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What is the connection between rifampicin and coronaviruses?

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

Rifampicin might be useful in the management of patients hospitalized for suspected COVID-19, because of its wide antimicrobial activity, for the treatment of possible bacterial co-infection.

Is rifampicin only useful for the treatment of possible bacterial co-infection, including tuberculosis (described in the study conducted by Low and coworkers), or rifampicin has additional antiviral effect on coronaviruses?

Further research is necessary to elucidate this question.

RIFAMPICIN

Rifampicin (rifampin) is an antibiotic used to treat several types of bacterial infections, including tuberculosis, *Mycobacterium avium* complex, leprosy, and Legionnaires' disease. It is almost always used together with other antibiotics, except when given to prevent *Haemophilus influenzae type B* and meningococcal disease in people who have been exposed to those bacteria. Rifampicin may be given either by mouth or intravenously¹.

Rifampicin inhibits bacterial DNA-dependent RNA synthesis by inhibiting bacterial DNA-dependent RNA polymerase².

Rifampicin has some effectiveness against vaccinia virus^{3, 4}.

RIFAMPICIN AND CORONAVIRUSES

Authors of the study (Bleibtreu, et al) concluded that empirical treatment with neuraminidase inhibitors and an association of antibiotics, including **rifampicin**, effective against *S. pneumoniae* and *L. pneumophila* are the cornerstones of the management of patients hospitalized for suspected MERS-CoV infection⁵.

Ruediger Buchkremer started discussion on Research Gate about his study that reveals the **NTM (Pulmonary nontuberculous mycobacterial) disease**. NTM reveals almost the same symptoms as compared to later-stage symptoms after a coronavirus infection (including ground-glass opacities on CT scans). Even if it is not 100% analog, he suggests, maybe the treatments that cure NTM also cure COVID-19 (e. g. rifamycin, rifabutin, rifampin⁶).

In Singapore, of 236 patients with probable severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS), 2 were co-infected with tuberculosis and successfully treated with rifampicin, isoniazid, pyrazinamide, and ethambutol.

The patients' tuberculosis episodes only came to light after full recovery from SARS, when they presented with persistent

respiratory symptoms and/or worsening chest radiography findings⁷.

CONCLUSION

Rifampicin might be useful in the management of patients hospitalized for suspected COVID-19, because of its wide antimicrobial activity, just like it was described in the study (Bleibtreu, et al) as one of the antibiotics to be given as cornerstone of the management of patients hospitalized for suspected MERS-CoV infection.

Is rifampicin only useful for the treatment of possible bacterial co-infection, including tuberculosis (described in the study conducted by Low and coworkers), or rifampicin has additional antiviral effect on coronaviruses?

Further research is necessary to elucidate this question.

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